

Empowering Latin American Networks to Champion Open and Equitable Scholarly Preprint and Dataset Review

Project Impact and Alignment

This project aims to empower Spanish- and Portuguese-speaking research communities in Latin America to lead a transformation in how research is evaluated, focusing on preprints and datasets. [MetaDocencia](#) and [PREreview](#) will collaborate, building on their shared experience in capacity building, community-centered training, and the development of open, human-centered infrastructure that supports equitable participation in open science.

Over three years, the project will move through three interconnected phases: 1) research and community-informed development; 2) a series of Spanish-language *Champions Programs* designed to empower researchers to act as local multipliers; 3) adaptation of all materials and activities for Portuguese-speaking communities. Measures of impact will include the number of trainings delivered, participation rates, events attended, research groups and networks onboarded, and the number of preprint and dataset reviews posted on PREreview from the region.

Preprints are reshaping scholarly communication by enabling free, early dissemination. Platforms like SciELO Preprints are accelerating their adoption in Latin America. PREreview supports this shift as the only free, open-source, journal- and server-independent platform for multilingual, community-driven preprint review. *Through this project, researchers will learn to use open tools such as PREreview and SciELO Preprints and contribute to their development—particularly for open dataset review—through inclusive, multilingual design sprints and focused interviews.*

The project will help Latin American researchers engage more fully in global scientific dialogues and contribute their perspectives to pressing global challenges, as it challenges exclusionary, Global North-dominated systems of research evaluation that privilege English-language and Western norms. By contextualizing tools and training, validating non-English knowledge, and supporting historically underserved communities, the project promotes epistemic justice.

Furthermore, open peer review accelerates feedback and makes evaluation more transparent and inclusive—qualities critical to research aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals, including health, education, and climate.

By empowering regional actors to lead in the implementation of open evaluation practices, *the project will strengthen their roles in shaping human-centered open infrastructure and hubs for capacity-building. These networks will be better positioned to support researchers in accessing, producing, and sharing open knowledge.*

This project offers a unique blend of opportunities for researchers in Latin America—from regionally adapted train-the-trainer Champions programming to active participation in shaping open infrastructure—empowering them to lead the future of community-driven, open, and equitable peer review. It will also foster connections among individuals and groups with shared goals, strengthening local engagement and driving innovation.

Project Plan

The project will begin with team building, research, and a community-informed, iterative adaptation of the [PREreview Champions Program](#) into Latin American Spanish. In the second stage, we will deliver Spanish-language training to prepare groups of researchers as local multipliers, providing mentoring and financial support for them to lead their own activities while

gathering feedback to improve the program. Finally, we will onboard Brazilian communities and collaboratively adapt materials and activities for Portuguese-speaking audiences.

Timeline	Y1 (Oct25-Sep26)				Y2 (Oct26-Sep27)				Y3 (Oct27-Sep28)			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Staff recruiting and team building	■	■										
Research for network readiness and discovery sprints		■	■	■								
Contextualization of Spanish Champions Program			■	■								
Champions recruitment (20-25/cohort)				■	■		■					
Spanish Champions Programs (3 cohorts)					■		■		■			
Program assessment, community feedback						■		■		■		
Support delivery of multiplying activities						■	■	■	■	■	■	
Contextualization of Portuguese Champions Program									■	■		
Overall assessment of the program and report												■

Sustainability

Latin American research communities are uniquely positioned to lead the adoption of open publishing practices, building on a long tradition of community-led, publicly funded open access models. This project builds on that foundation, leveraging MetaDocencia’s and PREreview’s years of experience supporting the engagement of these communities with open science.

To ensure long-term sustainability, Champions will be selected through a careful application process designed to identify individuals whose interests and values align with the project’s goals, and who have institutional support to engage broader local networks. Beyond training, the team will work with each Champion to develop tailored strategies to sustain and grow their activities over time, empowering them to build local capacity for open preprint and dataset review. All Champions will be provided with financial compensation and support to carry on their multiplying activities throughout the project. Through this approach, the project invests not only in individuals but in durable systems of support that will extend the impact beyond the project’s formal end.

Community engagement

Recognizing that open peer review remains unfamiliar to many, the first year will be dedicated to deep listening—engaging researchers across the MetaDocencia Network to surface regional barriers, motivations, and needs. In the first research phase, MetaDocencia will reach out to close collaborators in their Network—[CICADA](#), [Nodo Nacional de Bioinformatica](#), [PsiNetLab](#), [OpenLabEcuador](#), to mention a few—to share about the scope and plan for the initiative, and invite them to provide their input and feedback through design sprints and discovery interviews—activities for which participants will be compensated. These insights will drive an adaptive, community-centered strategy focused on making participation meaningful and rewarding. Broader outreach throughout the program will leverage MetaDocencia’s and PREreview’s communication channels to highlight the tangible benefits of open peer review, from training and visibility to networking and career advancement, with the goal of growing awareness about the program and soliciting broader participation. Towards the final stage of the project, the ongoing partnership between PREreview and SciELO Preprints will be strengthened further, engaging SciELO Brazil and other Brazilian Portuguese-speaking communities in the translation and contextualization of the program to the needs and expectations of Brazilian researchers.

Network Readiness and Capacity

Experience with Shared Infrastructure

MetaDocencia brings deep expertise in community-centered open science [training](#) across Latin America, having delivered 94 training editions to over 1,500 participants from 33 countries, conducted 5 train-the-trainer programs, achieving a [Net Promoter Score](#) of 89%. They have [collaboratively contextualized](#) initiatives like [NASA's Open Science 101](#), involving multiple communities and independent researchers in the process. PREreview complements this with a strong record in global, community-centered peer review training, including 2 successful [Champion cohorts](#) and programs like [Open Reviewers in Africa](#), which reached over 200 researchers in the continent. Overall, PREreview has facilitated ethical peer review training reaching more than 800 researchers across 49 countries. Their experience in regional adaptation, human-centered technology design, and [ongoing localization of their platform into Latin American Spanish and Brazilian Portuguese](#) further strengthens the project's feasibility. Thanks to COAR Notify, a [technological integration connecting preprint servers like SciELO Preprints with PREreview](#), more than half of all review requests submitted to PREreview come from SciELO Preprints authors—almost all for content published in Spanish or Portuguese. This underscores the growing need to better connect researchers who have the time, knowledge, and skills to review with authors seeking feedback at a stage when it can meaningfully improve their work.

Community Governance

Both MetaDocencia and PREreview follow collaborative, equity-centered [governance](#) models that prioritize transparency and shared decision-making. MetaDocencia's structure—[co-designed with its community](#)—includes an Executive Team and an Advisory Committee (AC) of internal and external members with equal voting rights. The AC meets regularly to guide strategic decisions, with broader community participation encouraged. Its current membership includes a representative from [CICADA](#), a partner research center. PREreview uses a team-centric, self-managed model in which each team member holds decision-making authority within their area, supported by an advice process that incorporates input from affected stakeholders, including community members and collaborators. An AC provides organizational oversight and strategic input, and new members will be added to represent Latin American perspectives as PREreview expands its regional focus. Both organizations are rooted in community-developed principles of openness, equity, inclusion, and shared responsibility.

Commitment to Open Science and Open Infrastructure

Both MetaDocencia and PREreview are deeply committed to lowering barriers to participation in open science. MetaDocencia exemplifies this commitment through both its training and its internal practices. With over [200 openly shared outputs](#)—including [publications, data, code, and reports](#)—and a fully open website development process, MetaDocencia actively models sustainable, community-driven open science. Similarly, PREreview centers openness across all aspects of their work: partnerships and funding are transparently listed on its website; all content—including training materials, presentations, and publications—is openly available under a CC BY 4.0 license; and the preprint review platform itself is built on open-source code (MIT License) and hosted publicly on [GitHub](#). Reviews submitted through the platform are licensed under CC BY 4.0, deposited on Zenodo, and aligned with emerging metadata standards through collaborations with initiatives like COAR Notify and DocMaps. As openness is foundational to both organizations' approach, all outputs from this project will be openly licensed and hosted on open infrastructure.